

Convenient General Synthesis of α -Aminolunsaturated Ketones, Nitriles and their Use in Nenitzscue Indole Synthesis

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Nenitzscue indole synthesis needs enamines of primary amines having electron-withdrawing substituent on β -carbon of the enamine¹. Generally, enamines employed in this synthesis have substituent on α -carbon as they are prepared from β -oxoesters. Enamines containing cyano or keto group are generally difficult to prepare. Nenitzscue indole synthesis gives a maximum of 35% yield of the product. Enamines having no substituent on α -carbon are difficult to prepare.

Wolfbeis² and later, Hartmann and Scerny³ independently developed a convenient method for the synthesis of enamines using a three-component system containing a compound with an active methylene group, trimethyl orthoformate and a primary amine. It is reported that enamines with an ester group on β -carbon can readily be decarboalkoxylated⁴ without affecting other functionalities, thus giving a new convenient in situ synthesis⁵ of enamines from primary amines having electron-withdrawing substituent on β -carbon but with no substituent on α -carbon.

Results and Discussion

Following the above method the synthesis of some enamines and their corresponding indole derivatives have been discussed in the present communication. Thus primary amine when treated with a mixture of trimethyl orthoformate and active methylene compound (1) gives the corres-

ponding azomethylated product (2) which readily undergoes decarboethoxylation on heating in dimethylformamide containing a few drops of water to give 3. The in situ reaction of 3 with quinones (6 and 8) gives the corresponding indole derivatives. Further reactions of *N*-arylenamines (3d and 3f) having a keto group on α -carbon with *p*-benzoquinone under Nenitzscue indole synthesis are reported⁶ to give benzofuran derivatives (4) instead of the indoles (5).

But the present observation is not in agreement with the above fact. Both 5d and 7d did not undergo hydrolysis indicating that under the experimental conditions, the corresponding benzofurans (4a and 4b) are not formed. However, the spectral data and elemental analysis indicate the formation of indoles 5 and 7.

Experimental

All m.p.s. were taken by open capillary method and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on Beckmann Acculab-1 and Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometers and pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on Varian EM-360 L and Perkin-Elmer R-32 instruments using TMS as an internal standard.

Preparation of enamines (2). General method : Ethyl 2-cyano-3-(3-methoxyphenylamino)acrylate : A mixture of **1** (0.05 mol), trimethyl orthoformate (10 ml) and substituted-aniline (0.05 mol) was refluxed for 3–4 h and then cooled to room temperature. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (85–90%) : **2a**, m.p. 107–08°, ν_{\max} 2 210, 1 690, 3 260, 1 600 cm⁻¹; **2b**, 115°, ν_{\max} 1 690, 3 300 cm⁻¹; **2c**, 122°, ν_{\max} 1 690, 760 cm⁻¹; **2d**, 144°, ν_{\max} 1 690, 1 670, 3 400 cm⁻¹; **2e**, 130°, ν_{\max} 1 690, 760 cm⁻¹; **2f**, 220°, ν_{\max} 1 650, 3 300 cm⁻¹.

Indoles (5) and (7) : Reaction of quinones **6** and **8** with **2a–f** (through the in situ formation of **3**) : A solution of enamine (0.01 mol) in DMF (10 ml) containing few drops of water was refluxed for ~4 h. To it was added a solution of **6** or **8** (0.01 mol) in DMF (2 ml). The mixture was refluxed for ~5 h. Excess of DMF was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was quenched in excess cold water. A brown coloured solid thus obtained was washed with water and methanol successively, and crystallised from ethyl acetate to yield the corresponding indoles **5** and **7** (50–60%) : **5a**, m.p. >300°, ν_{\max} 2 200 cm⁻¹; δ 3.9 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.1–7.8 (H, m, ArH), 8.1 (1H, s, HA);

5b, >300°, ν_{\max} 1 695, 3 360 cm⁻¹; δ 1.2 (3H, t, C-CH₃), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.2 (2H, q, OCH₂), 7.25–7.98 (7H, m, ArH), 8.1 (1H, s, HA); **5c**, 259°, ν_{\max} 1 715, 3 320, 755 cm⁻¹; δ 1.38 (3H, t, C-CH₃), 4.15 (2H, q, O-CH₂), 7.1–7.85 (7H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, s, HA); **5d**, 284°, ν_{\max} 1 720, 3 310 cm⁻¹; δ 8.1 (1H, s, HA); **5e**, 232°, ν_{\max} 1 730, 3 330, 745 cm⁻¹; δ 2.1 (3H, s, COCH₃), 7.4–7.8 (H, m, ArH), 8.1 (1H, s, HA); **7a**, 142–43°, ν_{\max} 2 200, 3 200, 750 cm⁻¹; δ 4.1 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.3–7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, s, HA); **7b**, 230°, ν_{\max} 1 730, 3 340, 730 cm⁻¹; δ 1.2 (3H, t, C-CH₃), 3.95 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.2 (2H, q, OCH₃), 7.25–7.98 (8H, m, ArH), 8.25 (1H, s, HA); **7c**, 110–11°, ν_{\max} 710, 770, 1 690, 3 310 cm⁻¹; δ 1.3 (3H, t, C-CH₃), 4.2 (2H, q, OCH₂), 6.9–7.8 (8H, m, ArH), 8.1 (1H, s, HA); **7d**, 240°, ν_{\max} 1 710, 735, 3 280 cm⁻¹; δ 2.2 (3H, s, COCH₃), 7.3–8.0 (H, m, ArH), 8.3 (1H, s, HA).

All compounds gave satisfactory microanalytical results for C, H, N and Cl.

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